

Aggression, anger and hostility: evaluation of moral disengagement as a mediational process

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Abstract

This study examines how the mechanisms underlying moral disengagement serve as a mediator between anger and hostility and physical and verbal aggression. The study was carried out on 424 participants (61.1% females), aged 15 to 25 years, assessing the direct and indirect effects of the distinct variables using a hierarchical multiple regression analysis and structural equation modeling. The findings suggest that anger and hostility contribute independently and positively to physical and verbal aggression. Moreover, the relationships between anger, hostility, and aggression appear to be mediated by moral disengagement. Indeed, this process of mediation was invariant across sexes, and it tended to be stronger for physical—as opposed to verbal—aggression.

Keywords: Moral disengagement, adolescent, aggression, anger, hostility.

Introduction

Various theoretical approaches have shown that aggression is caused by multiple factors, in which distinct elements intervene, such as: emotions (i.e., anger, negative affect), cognition (i.e., appraisal, attribution, memories, beliefs, attitudes and values), self-regulation (i.e., moral self-sanctions, self-control, self-awareness, blame, shame),

and environmental factors (i.e., exposure to violent surroundings, psychosocial stress, aversive stimulation) (see Anderson & Huesmann, 2003; Bandura, 1983, 1986; Berkowitz, 1990, 1993; DeWall, Anderson, & Bushman, 2012, for a general review). Of all these elements, anger (as an emotional component) and hostility (as a cognitive component) have predominant roles in the appearance of aggressive behaviors. Anger is a negative emotion that varies in intensity from slight irritation or moderate annoyance to rage or fury, and the underlying psychobiological events are associated with strong psychophysiological activation. By contrast, hostility refers to feelings of resentment, suspicion, and alienation (Berkowitz, 1993; Buss & Perry, 1992; Spielberger, Jacobs, Russell, & Crane, 1983).

According to the *AHA Syndrome Theory* (Spielberger et al., 1983), anger, hostility, and aggression form part of a continuum represented by three components of manifest aggression (emotional, cognitive, and behavioral). Thus, an event that gives rise to anger and hostility can result in an aggressive action. Alternatively, and from a cognitive perspective, the *Cognitive Neoassociation Theory* (Berkowitz, 1990, 1993) emphasizes how the automatic stimulation of thoughts, memories, expressive-motor reactions, and physiological responses may have negative effects, which in turn generate rudimentary feelings of anger and hostility that result in aggressive actions. In short, both anger and hostility are important antecedents to aggressive behavior, although these variables also seem to be affected by self-regulatory processes, as demonstrated from the *cognitive-social* perspective (Bandura, 1986, 1990).

Accordingly, there are both cognitive (e.g., self-sanctions) and social (e.g., moral and behavioral norms) self-regulatory elements that mediate in the consequences of specific circumstances (e.g., negative affect, personality, stress) and aggression. At present, the *General Aggression Model* (GAM) provides an integrative, parsimonious, and unified

framework for domain-specific aggression theories (Anderson & Bushman, 2002) that draws heavily on social-cognitive and social learning theories (Bandura, 1986, 1990; Berkowitz, 1990, 1993). The GAM incorporates biology, personality, situational variables, and a variety of processes (i.e. social, basic cognitive, short and long-term, and decision) into understanding aggression (De Wall et al., 2012).

Most individuals have values, moral norms, and self-regulatory mechanisms (e.g., self-sanctions, self-awareness, self-image, or self-esteem) that regulate behavior and inhibit aggression (Anderson, 2000; Anderson & Huesmann, 2003; Bandura, 1983, 1986). Nevertheless, the self-regulatory processes can be partially or completely deactivated by various socio-cognitive mechanisms that facilitate the breaking of rules and the emergence of anti-social and aggressive behaviors in adolescents (Bandura, 1986, 1990; Bandura, Barbaranelli, Caprara, & Pastorelli, 1996; Hyde, Shaw, & Moilanen, 2010; Obermann, 2011a, 2011b) and adults (McAlister, Bandura, & Owen, 2006; South & Wood, 2006; Vollum & Buffington-Vollum, 2010). Deactivation of such self-regulatory process has been called *moral disengagement* (MD) and “refers to the use of different legitimization mechanisms conducive to a selective disengagement of moral censure” (Obermann, 2011b, p. 134). In other words, MD involves the use of cognitive mechanisms and attitudes to justify aggressive and immoral behavior. Indeed, as Anderson perceptively indicated (2000), these mechanisms “short-circuit” normal self-regulatory moral processes and render them irrelevant, facilitating the appearance of aggressive or morally reprehensible behaviors.

Recently, MD has been investigated as a mediator between certain antecedents and aggression. For example, MD was found to play a mediating role in how factors like peer rejection in adolescence influence criminal behavior in adulthood (Fontaine, Fida, Paciello, Tisak, & Caprara, 2014), and between childrearing practices in early

childhood and subsequent anti-social behavior (Pelton, Gound, Forehand, & Brody, 2004). In the intrapersonal sphere, the mediating role of MD between certain variables (i.e., hostile rumination and irritability) and aggression (Caprara et al., 2014) has also been investigated. In this context, moral disengagement seems to be crucial in opening the way towards aggressive behaviors. In addition, anger and hostility contribute to and affect deregulation and cognitive distortion, including the MD mechanisms conducive to detrimental behavior (Caprara et al., 2013; Paciello, Fida, Tramontano, Lupinetti, & Caprara, 2008). However, there are few studies that have specifically analyzed MD as a mediator in relation to different types of aggression (e.g., physical versus verbal).

Focusing on the antecedents described above, this study aimed to analyze the mediating role of MD between two of the precursors of aggression—anger and hostility—and between actual physical and verbal aggression. Thus, four relations mediated by MD were analyzed: anger and physical aggression, anger and verbal aggression, hostility and physical aggression, and hostility and verbal aggression. To test these relations, different alternative models were explored through structural equation models. Given that levels of aggression in adolescents and young adults tend to be higher in men than in women (Andreu, Peña, & Graña, 2002; Card, Stucky, Sawalani, & Little, 2008; Gerbino, Caprara, & Caprara, 2006), and that boys are more likely to employ MD mechanisms than girls (Bandura et al., 1996; De Caroli & Sagoni, 2014; Grussendorf, McAlister, Sandström, Udd, & Morrison, 2002; McAlister et al., 2006; Obermann, 2011b), the invariance of the proposed model was analyzed as a function of sex. We expected to find that experiencing anger and hostility would activate MD mechanisms, which in turn would facilitate physical and verbal aggressive behavior. Given the absence of previous research in this field, it was not possible to

establish a specific hypothesis regarding aggression (physical versus verbal) and sex (boys versus girls).

Method

Participants

This study was carried out on a sample of 424 participants (61.1% females), aged 15 to 25 years of age (average age 18.80; standard deviation 2.69). The study participants were Caucasian Spanish of middle socioeconomic status and were selected using non-probability sampling at various educational centers. All participants were volunteers and were not given any form of compensation.

Instruments

Moral disengagement. Moral disengagement was measured with the Mechanisms of Moral Disengagement Scale (MMDS; Bandura et al., 1996; Spanish version, Autor A, Autor C, & Autor B, manuscript under review). The MMDS was developed to evaluate how moral disengagement affects violent and transgressive behavior, either directly or indirectly, using other constructs that lead to aggression (e.g., blame, prosocial orientation, or emotional reactions). It consists of 32 items, each assessed using a five point Likert scale: 1- Fully disagree, 2- Disagree more than agree, 3- Neither agree nor disagree, 4- Agree more than disagree, 5- Fully agree. Items refer to different general beliefs in an interpersonal context with moral implications among adolescents including the protection of friends, joking or teasing, damaging or stealing some property, misbehaving in school or within their family, or insults among children. The scale enables us to obtain a general composite MD score and eight partial scores, one for each MD mechanism: *Moral Justification* (e.g., “It is all right to fight to protect

your friends”), *Euphemistic Language* (e.g., “Slapping and shoving someone is just a way of joking”), *Advantageous Comparison* (e.g., “Damaging some property is no big deal when you consider that others are beating people up”), *Displacement of Responsibility* (e.g., “If kids are living under bad conditions they cannot be blamed for behaving aggressively”), *Diffusion of Responsibility* (e.g., “A kid in a gang should not be blamed for the trouble the gang causes”), *Distortion of Consequences* (e.g., “It is okay to tell small lies because they don’t really do any harm”), *Attribution of Blame* (e.g., “If kids fight and misbehave in school it is their teacher’s fault”), and *Dehumanization* (e.g., “Some people deserve to be treated like animals. The general reliability of the instrument ranged from .82 to .93 in different studies when estimated by Cronbach’s alpha coefficient (Bandura et al., 1996; Bandura, Caprara, Barbaranelli, Pastorelli, & Regalia, 2001; Obermann, 2011a, 2011b; Pelton et al., 2004), and in this study, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was .88.

Anger, hostility, and aggression. Anger, hostility, and aggression were assessed with the Aggression Questionnaire (AQ; Buss & Perry, 1992; Spanish version, Andreu et al., 2002). The AQ has often been employed to evaluate aggressive behavior in adolescents and young adults, and in the detection of aggressive individuals in general populations (Andreu et al., 2002). Specifically, it allows us to obtain measurements of two types of aggression (*physical aggression and verbal aggression*) and of two emotions associated with aggressive behaviors, namely *anger* and *hostility* (Andreu et al., 2002). The questionnaire consists of 29 items that evaluate behavioral, cognitive and emotional aspects of aggression, scored on a 5 point Likert-type scale: 1 - Not at all like me; 2 - A little like me; 3 - Somewhat like me; 4 - Very much like me; 5 - Completely like me). It is divided into four subscales: *Physical Aggression* (e.g., “At times I can't control the urge to hit someone”), *Verbal Aggression* (e.g., “When people

annoy me, I may tell them what I think of them”), *Anger* (e.g., “I flare up quickly”), and *Hostility* (e.g., “I know that ‘friends’ talk about me behind my back”). The instrument has been shown to be psychometrically reliable and to display a strong overall internal consistency, both in its original version ($\alpha = .89$) and in its Spanish version ($\alpha = .88$). The confirmatory factor analysis of the Spanish version demonstrated its four-dimensional structure and its validity for measuring physical and verbal aggression and anger and hostility (Andreu et al., 2002). In the sample studied here, the overall reliability estimated by means of Cronbach's alpha coefficient was .89, and the following reliability coefficients were obtained for the different subscales: physical aggression (.87), verbal aggression (.72), anger (.74), and hostility (.74).

Procedure

The data were collected at the educational centers by three experienced investigators. Collective assessments were made in groups of 20 to 30 participants during school time, having first obtained the corresponding informed consent, which, in the case of minors, was given by parents, guardians, or legal representatives. Participation was voluntary, and prior to the evaluation, the overall aim of the study was explained, and general instructions on how to complete the evaluation instruments were provided. Throughout the procedure, the confidentiality of the information that was obtained and the anonymity of the participants was guaranteed.

Statistical Approach

Initially, sex differences for each of the study variables were analyzed using the *Student's t* test as a function of the sex of the participants. Subsequently, Pearson's correlations and hierarchical multiple regression analyses were used to perform a preliminary analysis. In accordance with the recommendations elsewhere (Baron &

Kenny, 1986), mediation was analyzed in three different models using structural equation modeling, and the effect size was estimated by the kappa-squared (Preacher and Kelley, 2011). The first step of this modeling was to show that the criterion (physical and verbal aggression) could be forecasted by the predictors (anger and hostility). The second step set out to assess whether the mediator (moral disengagement) could be predicted by anger and hostility. In the third step, we tested whether, when the mediator (moral disengagement) was included in the model, the effects of the antecedents (anger and hostility) on the criterion (physical and verbal aggression) were either strongly reduced or non-existent. To examine whether the original mediational model suggested was preferred to other similar models with different directional effects, we tested three alternative models: reverse model ($Y \rightarrow M \rightarrow X$), mediator-antecedent-criterion model ($M \rightarrow X \rightarrow Y$), and mediator-criterion-antecedent model ($M \rightarrow Y \rightarrow X$). Finally, the invariance of the parameters according to the sex of the young adults and adolescents was assessed through hierarchical structural equation modeling analysis. All the statistical analyses were performed using *LISREL 8.71* and *SPSS 15 for Windows* software.

Results

Preliminary analysis

The differences of the means between sexes were first calculated using the *Student's t* test and as a preliminary analysis, the correlation between these factors was assessed with a Pearson's rank correlation (Table 1) and through hierarchical multiple regression (Table 2). The results of the *Student's t* tests highlighted significant differences between males and females for the variables *moral disengagement*, *physical aggression*, and *verbal aggression*. Specifically, the males obtained higher average

scores than the females in *moral disengagement* [$M = 70.8$ ($SD = 18.0$) versus $M = 60.3$ ($SD = 14.5$); $t_{(422)} = 6.56, p < .05$], and they demonstrated a greater tendency towards *verbal aggression* [$M = 14.4$ ($SD = 3.5$) versus $M = 13.2$ ($SD = 3.8$); $t_{(422)} = 3.36, p < .05$] and *physical aggression* [$M = 21.7$ ($SD = 7.8$) versus $M = 16.3$ ($SD = 6.3$); $t_{(422)} = 7.79, p < .05$]. However, statistically significant sex differences were not detected for *hostility* ($p = .32$) or *anger* ($p = .39$). All of the correlations between variables of interest were significant and positive. Specifically, anger and hostility were related to both moral disengagement and physical and verbal aggression. In addition, moral disengagement was associated with physical and verbal aggression, and both physical and verbal aggression were also significantly related to one another.

Table 1

Basic Characteristics of the Sample and Correlations

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Anger	---				
2. Hostility	.42**	---			
3. Moral disengagement	.36**	.32**	---		
4. Physical aggression	.48**	.31**	.55**	---	
5. Verbal aggression	.59**	.35**	.40**	.49**	---
Mean	19.42	22.42	64.42	18.40	13.67
Standard deviation	5.26	5.84	16.78	7.41	3.74

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

Multiple hierarchical regression analysis was performed to explore the main contribution of antecedent variables (independent and mediator) to (physical and verbal) aggression and their possible mediating effects. Independent variables (anger and hostility) were included in step 1 and the mediator (moral disengagement) in step 2.

Table 2

Hierarchical regression analyses predicting physical and verbal aggression

	Physical Aggression				Verbal Aggression			
	Const.	β	R^2	ΔR^2	Const.	β	R^2	ΔR^2
Step 1								
Anger	2.96*	.43**	.24	.24**	4.41**	.54**	.36	.36**
Hostility		.12**				.11**		
Step 2								
Anger	-3.37*	.31**	.39	.15**	2.88**	.49**	.40	.04**
Hostility		.03				.07		
Moral Disengagement		.42**				.20**		

Note. Step 1: Independent variables; Step 2 = Mediator.

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

As evident in Table 2, anger and hostility each make an independent and positive contribution to physical and verbal aggression, and moral disengagement was significantly and positively associated with both physical and verbal aggression. Furthermore, when moral disengagement was included in step 2, the contribution of anger and hostility changed, whereby the contribution of anger to aggression decreased and hostility was no longer significant. Indeed, this was the case for both physical as well as verbal aggression. These findings suggest that moral disengagement has a mediating effect between anger and hostility, and between physical and verbal aggression.

Direct and Mediating Effects

In order to further test these mediating effects, we propose a model that includes anger and hostility as antecedents, moral disengagement as a mediator, and physical and verbal aggression as criterion variables (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Standardized solution for anger and hostility, and physical and verbal aggression including moral disengagement as mediator

We first tested model 1.1, which represents the direct effects between the antecedents and the criterion factors after constraining all of the indirect paths. The relations between anger and hostility and adolescent outcomes were similar for physical and verbal aggression (model 1.1). Significant direct effects were evident between anger and both physical aggression ($c = .43$, $CR = 10.03$) and verbal aggression ($c = .55$, $CR = 14.67$). Likewise, the direct effects between hostility and aggression were significant for physical ($c = .13$, $CR = 2.76$) and verbal aggression ($c = .10$, $CR = 2.79$). Therefore, anger and hostility have a significant and direct effect on physical and verbal aggression.

In the next step we tested model 1.2, which represents the direct paths between antecedents and mediators after constraining the paths from moral disengagement (mediator) to physical and verbal aggression (variables) in the subjects to zero. These direct effects were significant from anger to moral disengagement ($c = .27$, $CR = 5.75$), as well as from hostility to moral disengagement ($c = .21$, $CR = 4$).

Finally, we assessed the mediation model in which all the parameters were allowed to vary (the unconstrained model, model 1.3: Figure 1). In this model only anger (not hostility) predicts (physical and verbal) aggression in young adults and adolescents. Moreover, there was a decrease in the coefficients for mediation in the direct paths from anger to physical aggression ($c = .43$ versus $c' = .32$), and to verbal aggression ($c = .55$ versus $c' = .49$). The relationship between hostility and aggression in young adults and adolescents was mediated by moral disengagement, and the direct effects of hostility on aggression were no longer significant. These results suggested that the relationships between anger and hostility and adolescent aggression were mediated significantly by moral disengagement (see Figure 1 for the standardized coefficients and the significance of the different paths). All of the indirect effects were

significant in terms of the association from anger to both physical ($ab = .12$, $CR = 4.91$; $\kappa^2 = .081$) and verbal aggression ($ab = .06$, $CR = 3.67$; $\kappa^2 = .076$); and from hostility to physical ($ab = .09$, $CR = 3.93$; $\kappa^2 = .070$) and verbal aggression ($ab = .04$, $CR = 3.21$; $\kappa^2 = .066$). Although the mediation effect sizes conducted by kappa squared measure (κ^2) were medium and similar for all indirect effects, the mediating effects tended to be stronger when anger (rather than hostility) was considered as an antecedent variable. Therefore, hostility and especially anger tended to increase moral disengagement, which was subsequently conducive to aggression in young adults and adolescents.

The fit in the unconstrained model was perfect when the parameters were estimated freely ($\chi^2 = 0.00$; $df = 2$; $p = 1.00$; *Root Mean Square Error of Approximation* [RMSEA] = .000), and the standardized regression coefficients were relatively strong and significant (see Figure 1). Similarly, the significant decrease ($p < .001$) in the Chi-squared test, as well as in the RMSEA fit index between the unrestricted model 1.3, and models 1.1 ($\chi^2 = 220.10$; $df = 6$; $p = .000$; RMSEA = .29) and 1.2 ($\chi^2 = 706.07$; $df = 9$; $p = .00$; RMSEA = .42), suggested that the unrestricted model better represented the data. Hence, moral disengagement appeared to mediate between anger and hostility and aggression.

Alternative models

Three alternative models were examined to test whether the suggested mediational model (Model 1.3, see Figure 1) was preferred to three other models with different directional effects. Model 2 was a complete reverse model, in which all the paths in the original model were turned in the other direction ($\chi^2 = 0.00$; $df = 2$; $p = 1.00$; RMSEA = .00). Model 3 was a mediator-antecedent-criterion model, in which MD was taken as antecedent, anger and hostility as mediators, and physical and verbal

aggression as criterion variables ($\chi^2 = 0.52$; $df = 2$; $p = .769$; RMSEA = .00). Finally, model 4 was a mediator-criterion-antecedent model, in which MD was taken as antecedent, physical and verbal aggression as mediators, and anger and hostility as criterion ($\chi^2 = 0.52$; $df = 2$; $p = .769$; RMSEA = .00).

Model 1 and model 2 obtained the best fit to the data, and both supported the MD as a potential mediational process. According to model 2, physical aggression significantly predicted anger ($c = .23$, $CR = 4.87$) but not hostility ($c = .10$, $CR = 1.74$), and verbal aggression significantly predicted both anger ($c = .46$, $CR = 11.44$) and hostility ($c = .23$, $CR = 4.49$). Relations between physical aggression and hostility ($ab = .08$, $CR = 3.12$), and between verbal aggression and hostility ($ab = .03$, $CR = 2.51$), were significantly mediated by MD. Nonsignificant indirect effects of MD were found between physical aggression and anger ($ab = .02$, $CR = 1.03$) and verbal aggression and anger ($ab = .01$, $CR = 1.00$).

The other two models (Model 3 and 4) were acceptable in terms of fit; however, no paths in either were significant, including the indirect effects.

Both the original and reverse models could be accepted from a statistical perspective. However, considering that various causal mechanisms may be conceivable in the mediation setting, and the term “causal” refers to inference on mediation effects based on a hypothesized directionality, we can theoretically establish the preferred directions (Imai, Keele, Tingley, & Yamamoto, 2011). Thus, from a theoretical approach, both anger and hostility have been supported as antecedents of aggression rather than outcomes (Berkowitz, 1993; Spielberger et al., 1983), even from a developmental and temperamental perspective (Gartstein, Putnam, & Rothbart, 2012; Zhou, Main, & Wang, 2010).

Analysis of Invariance as a Function of the Participants' Sex

In a theoretical model of boys and girls separately (Figure 1), the inferential χ^2 test value for boys was 0.00 ($p = .10$; $df = 2$) and the RMSEA = .00. Likewise, the inferential test result for girls was $\chi^2 = 0.00$ ($p = .10$; $df = 2$) with a RMSEA fit index = .00. This indicates that the model has a good fit for both sexes. When boys and girls were included together in the analysis, the multi-group comparison revealed that the goodness-of-fit indices for the baseline model were $\chi^2 = 0.00$ ($p = 1.00$; $df = 4$). If we consider only the χ^2 value, we would be able to accept the same structure independent of sex. Finally, we explored the invariance of the parameters that constrain the equality of the pattern of coefficients, which produced a $\chi^2 = 8.05$ ($p = .97$; $df = 17$). Therefore, the χ^2 increment, with respect to the baseline model, was not significant ($\Delta\chi^2 = 8.05$, $\Delta df = 13$, $p = .84$), which indicated that the parameters were statistically invariant with regard to sex.

Discussion

This study analyzed MD as a mediational process between two factors that predicted or facilitated aggression, namely anger and hostility, and actual physical and verbal aggression. Besides confirming the predictive value of anger and hostility with respect to aggression, the results obtained showed that these relationships were mediated significantly by MD.

Since the original and reverse model both fit the data quite well on this cross-sectional design, the direction of effects in the model can only be granted on theoretical bases (Imai et al., 2011). In this regard, many theoretical models of aggression have established anger and hostility as potential antecedents of aggression (Berkowitz, 1993; Buss & Perry, 1992; Spielberger et al., 1983).

The direct and significant relationships between anger and hostility and physical and verbal aggression found here coincided with previous findings (Anderson & Bushman, 2002; Archer, 2004; Berkowitz, 1990; Norlander & Eckhardt, 2005; Spielberger et al., 1983), whereby an increase in anger and hostility in turn augments the levels of aggression. Likewise, the direct and significant relationship between MD and physical or verbal aggression was also consistent with other previous findings (Bandura et al., 1996; Bandura et al., 2001; Paciello et al., 2008), encouraging us to regard anger, hostility and MD as crucial risk factors for the appearance of aggressive behaviors.

Over and above these well-established, direct relationships, few studies have focused on the processes that might explain this situation. The data we have presented here have demonstrated that MD constituted a significant factor mediating both the relationships between anger and aggression, and those between hostility and aggression. In other words, the sensation of anger and hostility facilitated the activation of MD mechanisms that promote aggressive behaviors. It is possible that, in accordance with what has been theoretically proposed elsewhere, MD mechanisms eliminated cognitive dissonance and moral self-censorship, preserving one's self-esteem and minimizing personal responsibility (Caprara, Fida, Vecchione, Tramontano, & Barbaranelli, 2009; De Caroli & Sagone, 2014), as well as promoting emotional and cognitive reactions that lead to aggression (Bandura et al., 1996; Obermann, 2011b). It would thus be interesting to include other variables such as self-esteem and cognitive dissonance in future research on MD and aggression. These results suggest that the deactivation of self-regulatory processes through MD constitutes a crucial element that underlies the consistent relationship between anger/hostility and aggression. From a theoretical perspective, the effects of anger on certain cognitive variables (e.g., attributions,

appraisals, schematic conceptions) that enhance aggressive inclinations have been well established, such as in the cognitive neoassociation model (Berkowitz, 1990) or the two-factor theory of emotion (Schachter & Singer, 1962). Previous studies presented evidence of the mediational role of MD (Fontaine et al., 2014; Pelton et al., 2004), particularly between irritability or hostile rumination and violence (Caprara et al., 2014). Indeed, when the longitudinal relationships between irritability, hostile rumination, and moral disengagement were analyzed in 345 young adults, irritability and hostile rumination contributed to the development of each of these behaviors reciprocally, and in a significant manner over time (Caprara et al., 2014). In addition, hostile rumination and moral disengagement significantly mediated in the relationship between irritability and violence, while moral disengagement significantly mediated in the relationship between hostile rumination and violence. However, that study did not include verbal and physical aggression as separate entities, and it also included different mediators in the same model, making it difficult to clearly establish the role of MD as a mediational process. In keeping with an earlier proposal (Bandura, 1986, 1990; Bandura et al., 1996), the results of our present study have supported the notion that MD mediated these aggressive behaviors. MD intervened by deactivating or reducing the effectiveness of the self-regulatory processes that inhibit aggressive and violent behavior in a network that associates anger, hostility, cognition, and actual aggression (Berkowitz, 1990, 1993).

An unexpected result was obtained when anger and hostility were compared, in that mediation was seen to be more robust for anger than hostility, a difference for which we have no clear explanation. In other words, anger, more than hostility, affects MD in such a way that tends to increase physical and verbal aggression. This could possibly be explained by anger (as a basic emotion) rather than hostility (as cognitive

component) being a more immediate precursor to aggressive behavior (Archer, 2004), and could be more difficult than hostility to keep under cognitive control. Moreover, hostility and MD share the cognitive features (Bandura et al., 1996; Buss & Perry, 1992; Spielberger et al., 1983). Therefore, hostility could increase the indirect effect on aggression less than anger. In any case, the effect sizes of this mediational process were similar between anger or hostility and aggression, and the different results between anger and hostility should be considered as a tendency. Further studies would be necessary to investigate why the mediational process of MD tend to be more robust when anger instead of hostility is considered.

The sex differences in the variables studied coincided with those described elsewhere: boys show higher levels of aggression (Andreu et al., 2002; Card et al., 2008; Gerbino et al., 2006) and moral disengagement than girls (Bandura et al., 1996; De Caroli & Sagoni, 2014; Grussendorf et al., 2002; McAlister et al., 2006; Obermann, 2011b). Nevertheless, the model that best represents the relationships between the study variables was similar for boys and girls, indicating that MD mechanisms act in a comparable way in both sexes. These findings were consistent with earlier results (Caprara et al., 2014), where no sex differences were found in the direct and indirect longitudinal effects between irritability, hostile rumination and violence.

The study presented here has certain limitations, amongst which we might emphasize the exclusive use of self-report measures in an interpersonal context among adolescents and the fact that these measures were cross-sectionally obtained. This limitation explained why the use of proxy-report measures is particularly recommended for exteriorized behaviors (Achenbach, McConaughy, & Howell, 1987; Kolko & Kazdin, 1993). In the self-report measure used, MD is assessed in specific interpersonal situations. Adolescents may report different levels of MD in different situations.. Future

studies should explore the MD from specific situations that adolescents are better able to keep in mind or imagine. Moreover, to confirm the mediational relationships established, longitudinal designs should be used (Baron & Kenny, 1986); a longitudinal design enables us to ensure that the order and temporal sequence proposed in the model occurs in the manner hypothesized. Nevertheless, even when both the predictor and the mediator are under the control of the experimenter, causal interpretation may still be questionable (Bullock, Green, & Ha, 2010). Additionally, from a methodological perspective, temporal order of events is not a sufficient condition for causation, and longitudinal designs for mediational analysis are not free of biases (Maxwell, Cole, & Mitchell, 2011). For these reasons, the suggested mediational model tries to establish the extent to which the hypothesized inferences are consistent with the data (Bollen, 1989) rather than establishing causal relations. According to this approach, the term “causal” refers to the inference regarding the direction of mediation effects based on a hypothesized directionality. Structural equation modeling is a statistical approach and cannot afford a final proof of a true causal model.

Despite these limitations, this study is coherent with the established theoretical models in this field, and the results are consistent with previous findings. In one way or another, these results will help to improve our knowledge of the processes that underlie the relationships between anger, hostility, and aggression, thereby fostering a better understanding of the phenomenon of aggression in young adults. The mediational model established here therefore transcends the mere establishment of relationships between these variables.

The main practical implication of this work was to show the relations of MD mechanisms on aggressive conduct in adolescents, especially when they experience anger or hostility. Anger and hostility can be the discriminant stimuli that activate the

MD mechanisms that in turn increase the adolescent's aggressive behaviors. Being aware of this mechanism or disrupting it could prevent the flow from anger or hostility to physical or verbal aggression. Therefore, it would be advisable to consider these socio-cognitive mechanisms as an important element to implement as primary or secondary violence prevention in programs for adolescents.

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